

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF STATE REGULATION ON THE FORMATION OF THE STATE'S INVESTMENT POLICY

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Abstract

It has been established that, to a large extent, the dynamics of the structure and the volume of Ukraine's real investments have been shaped by the investment policies pursued by the Government over different periods. High transaction costs and incomplete information disclosure in Ukraine give rise to significant moral hazard and adverse selection among institutional firms. The root cause lies in the weakness and corruption of the country's regulatory institutions.

This does not mean, however, that Ukraine lacks regulatory bodies or that they fail to cover all areas typically regulated in a modern market economy. The Ukrainian insurance system displays features of a transfer mechanism rather than a system of insurance funds, and continues to generate both economic and social challenges: low pension and welfare payments, as well as inadequate healthcare provision.

Moreover, this deprives the Ukrainian economy of a major potential source of investment capital—resources accumulated by social insurance funds—which is atypical for a modern market economy.

It should be emphasized that Ukraine's current institutional framework is far from optimal. This is largely due to the absence of the rule of law in the sphere of private and public relations, the lack of a high-quality judiciary, the low representativeness of political institutions, underdeveloped social partnership, and insufficient social insurance coverage.

Keywords: investment policy, state regulation, management of the investment mechanism, investment climate, economic policy.

To a large extent, the dynamics of the structure and the volume of Ukraine's real investments were determined by the investment policies pursued by the Government in different years, which changed repeatedly during this period. The country's leadership did not have a clear understanding of the scope and consequences of decisions affecting the investment sphere, thereby shaping the investment climate in the country. An analysis of the models of state investment policy makes it possible to identify at each structural element of economic policy that determines the investment regime in the specific economic system, thereby reproducing the parameters of state regulation of investment in Ukraine and describing the state investment policy of Ukraine that has been latently implemented in these years [1].

In assessing the degree of favourability of Ukraine's institutional environment for investment, it should be noted that it is lower than in the USA, Japan, and even Taiwan. This is due to the fact that, as the financial crisis has shown, creditors' rights are not protected in Ukraine, because, firstly, obtaining a court ruling on a company's insolvency (bankruptcy) usually takes more than 90 days; secondly, the assets of a company undergoing restructuring or bankruptcy proceedings in Ukraine are usually automatically frozen; thirdly, the claims of commercial creditors have lower priority in recovery than those of the state (tax arrears), social insurance funds, and company employees (wage arrears). The only provision that supports creditors' rights in current Ukrainian legislation is the requirement that, in the event of liquidation or bankruptcy, the company's managers be removed from management and external administrators be appointed.

As for the effectiveness of Ukraine's legal system in the field of private commercial law, it is also quite low, since restructuring in Ukraine is usually very slow, rather costly, procedurally complex, and its results are generally ineffective.

Thus, the degree of owners' control over the income from their assets in Ukraine is exceptionally low, which partly explains the general decline in investment activity in its economy, the low level of foreign direct investment, and the outflow of Ukrainian capital abroad.

High transaction costs and incomplete disclosure of information in Ukraine give rise to substantial risks of opportunistic behavior and adverse selection among institutional firms [2]. The underlying cause is the weakness and corruption of the country's state regulatory institutions. This does not imply, however, that Ukraine has few regulatory bodies or that they fail to cover the areas typically regulated in a modern market economy. On the contrary, Ukraine's economy is excessively overregulated: under its legislation, virtually any business activity requires licensing and is subject to oversight by multiple state agencies. However, the system underpinning the state's supervisory activities is not designed to improve the functioning of market contracting mechanisms, but instead serves primarily restrictive and fiscal purposes, rendering it highly inefficient.

Perhaps the only area in which Ukraine's institutional environment has approached the parameters of a modern market economy is the system of macroeconomic institutions currently in place. This is hardly surprising, as the bulk of market reforms

in Ukraine were carried out under the aegis of monetarism, whose doctrine in the field of state regulation behavior the achievement of macroeconomic stability as a necessary precondition for the formation of a market economy. However, as practice has shown, their existence has ceased to be a sufficient condition for ensuring Ukraine's economic growth.

As for Ukraine's social insurance institutions, this aspect of the institutional environment, although established from scratch during the reform period, still bears the imprint of socialist (communist) ideology with regard to the recipients of public insurance services against social and economic risks. The Ukrainian system of social insurance institutions has retained the "common pool" principle in the formation of insurance funds, whereby resources collected from all payers are redistributed among those entitled to receive social benefits [3]. As a result, the Ukrainian insurance system retains the features of a transfer mechanism rather than a system of dedicated insurance funds, and continues to generate both economic and social problems: low levels of pensions and benefits, as well as inadequate healthcare provision. Moreover, this deprives Ukraine's economy of a significant potential source of investment capital—resources accumulated by social insurance funds—which is not characteristic of a modern market economy.

It should be noted that the current set of institutions in Ukraine is far from perfect. This is largely due to the absence of the rule of law in the sphere of private and public relations, the lack of a high-quality judicial system, the low representativeness of political institutions, underdeveloped social partnership, and the insufficient level of social insurance [4]. At the same time, it should be acknowledged that over the past decade Ukraine has seen an increase in electoral freedom, the independence of trade unions, and the institutional representativeness of small social groups and national minorities.

The above analysis leads to the conclusion that, at present, Ukraine's institutional regime is unfavourable for productive and investment activity and is not oriented towards their stimulation.

With regard to microeconomic-level institutions responsible for directly behavior the Ukrainian capital market, they clearly illustrate the legal inconsistencies characteristic of Ukraine's institutional system as a whole. The main shortcomings of the laws intended to reduce information costs in Ukraine's capital market can be identified as follows [5]:

— The Law on Joint-Stock Companies in Ukrainian legislation is imperfect because, in carrying out various procedures related to the property aspects of these economic entities, it discriminates against the rights of certain categories of stakeholders, such as minority shareholders, commercial creditors, and others;

— The Law on Securities in Ukraine, on the one hand, mandates complex and costly registration procedures for issuance, while on the other hand, it does not require adequate disclosure of essential financial and business information about the issuer, which is unjustified from the standpoint of legal and economic efficiency. Moreover,

this law artificially restricts the range of securities permitted for circulation within Ukraine;

— Ukrainian legislation effectively lacks laws on the disclosure of commercial information, as the requirement for Ukrainian public joint-stock companies to publish their financial statements annually is insufficient by international standards in this regard;

— The laws governing the provision of state guarantees in Ukraine contain numerous procedural obstacles that hinder the protection of investors' interests (such as the referral and notification procedures in the event of a guarantee call, the creditor's right to take measures to locate the debtor's assets, compliance with pre-trial dispute resolution procedures, etc.), which reduces the functional effectiveness of this institution.

As for the imperfections of Ukrainian laws regulating contracting costs on the capital market, the following aspects should be noted:

— The Law on Investment Activity contains a low level of regulation regarding the general rules, rights, and obligations of all participants in contracting on the Ukrainian capital market, along with uncertainty or improper reduction of the legal status of certain investment process participants in favour of others (the state and joint-stock company administrations), which is unacceptable within Ukraine's codified legal system;

— Excessive liberalism in the laws on securities, banking and banking activities, and investment companies, with many transactions falling outside the scope of legal regulation (for example, futures contracts without delivery of the underlying asset);

— Excessive complexity of procedural matters in the legislation governing the provision of state guarantees for commercial transactions, combined with strict conditions defining the guarantor's (state's) obligation to pay the guarantee amount to the creditor (investor).

However, the greatest degree of incompleteness in Ukrainian legislation regulating the capital market pertains to the institutional risk mitigation mechanisms related to investment activity [6]. It can be asserted that:

— There are no laws protecting investors' interests in the securities market, regulating fiduciary relationships and contracts, insider trading with securities, nationalization, competition and restrictions on monopolistic activities in the capital market, or guaranteeing deposits and investment returns;

— The Ukrainian bankruptcy law — one of the main laws defining investment risks — does not comply with international commercial practice standards, thereby lowering the creditworthiness rating of the Ukrainian economy [7].

Thus, Ukraine's legal framework governing relations in the investment sphere requires significant revision and improvement. There is an urgent need for its behaviorization and for addressing the existing regulatory imbalances.

According to the doctrine of monetarism, an important role among the mechanisms for managing Ukraine's capital market was assigned to the policy of controlling the risk-free rate of return, while the regulation of risk premiums was left to market forces [8]. The primary instruments in this context were periodic issuances of government short-term obligations (GSO),

Eurodollar loans, and the refinancing rate set by the National Bank of Ukraine. The first two instruments were also used to finance Ukraine's budget deficit, thereby limiting the government's ability to employ them to stimulate industrial investment. Moreover, over time, as the burden of public debt became excessive for Ukraine's weak economy, GSOs effectively began crowding out funds from the country's industrial sector.

The low level of social protection necessitates additional savings motivated by economic and social caution. Therefore, the savings rate of Ukrainian households during the period was expected to be relatively high. The main channels absorbing citizens' savings were currency accumulation, capital flight abroad, and placement in the form of government borrowings. Thus, the existing social insurance system in Ukraine, despite its inefficient performance of core functions, significantly influences the savings behavior of Ukrainian families.

Regarding Ukraine's tax system, over the past decade it has exerted a notably disincentive effect on private savings—both household and corporate. This primarily concerns turnover taxes and indirect taxes, which reduce demand for the products they tax and thus exert a restraining influence on production, savings, and investment. Optimal measures to stimulate investment are considered to be public expenditures on infrastructure development, government contracts placed within the private sector, spending on R&D, and other expenditures aimed at increasing public capital. Unfortunately, government spending at various levels in Ukraine has largely been of a consumptive and subsidy nature, which has negatively impacted the level of national savings.

Regarding the institutions regulating economic activity at the macroeconomic level in the proposed Ukrainian model of state investment policy, it should be noted that, in accordance with the deficiencies identified to date, the following legal aspects should be reflected: the harmonization of all provisions regulating financial, economic, and social activities throughout the entire territory of Ukraine, regardless of regional specificities.

The principles of unconditional respect for property rights should form the foundation of economic activity; Ukrainian legislation must thoroughly address issues related to the monetary and currency regime in Ukraine, with the primary focus shifting from the

state's pursuit of economic power and economic autonomy over its citizens to ensuring the protection of property rights and the predictability of monetary and currency relations within the territory of Ukraine.

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